

PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL SATISFACTION AS A PREDICTOR OF WORK MOTIVATION OF EMPLOYEES AT THE MINISTRY OF HIGHER EDUCATION OF AFGHANISTAN

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Abstract

Individual performance appraisal satisfaction is the founding stone of the organization's progress and productivity. This base is strengthened by work motivation. The purpose of this study was to scrutinize those factors which boost the productivity of the Ministry of Higher Education's (MoHE) employees. Convenience sampling technique applied on Ministry's employees. Data were collected from 60 samples which consist of both sex (41 male, 19 female), their age ranged from (22-37), and their grade ranged from three to six of the participated employees in the study. The regression analysis, two-way ANOVA, and Pearson correlation were applied. The result proved that Performance appraisal satisfaction did a significant contribution to the work motivation at MoHE. The grade and gender of the participants did not have significant interaction with performance appraisal and motivation. Moreover, the association of age with performance appraisal and motivation also was not significant.

Keywords: Intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, employees Grade, MoHE

INTRODUCTION

Human resource is the core component of every organization. That leads the organization to its objectives and success to its everyday demand. Specifically, the Afghan government has initially started the new process of upgrading through many current academic and scientific paradigms some of these integral parts are the performance appraisal satisfaction, motivation, work preference, organization commitment, intention to leave, and many other aspects. Performance appraisal satisfaction paves the way for the achievement of any organization's mission, vision, and strategic goals.

Performance appraisal is the scientific multidimensional system that officially re-evaluates the current statuesque of an origination's individual, team, and group tasks which leads the administration's strategic goals. Even though, the upper managers and evaluation of team performance members do not like performance appraisal. Hence, most of the performance evaluations take place on an individual basis (Marcellin, 2019). Some authors are arguing that individual performance appraisal merges every employee's specific task and objectives to lead the organizational behaviour and its core goals (Addabbo et al., 2020). Motivation is also an unforgettable factor that cooperates with the performance appraisal system. Motivation is "the willingness to achieve organizational objectives". This will also support the organization's strategic objectives by positively raising the production of the organization (Marcellin, 2019, p. 54). Therefore evaluation of employees at MoHE is very important. Furthermore, American psychologist Frederick Irving Herzberg divided motivation into two parts. First "intrinsic motivation" second "extrinsic motivation" (Guillén, 2020, p. 4). Extrinsic motivation is those external phenomena that influence employees to do their job tasks more productively and intrinsic motivation is those inside influential factors which deliberately make an employee more productive (Guillén, 2020).

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Performance appraisal

Performance appraisal satisfaction has a significant association with motivation. Its weak relation provides the negative work performance, internal motivation, and the strong relationship showed a high level of motivation (Kuvaas, 2006). However, Marcellin (2019) proved some cons of the performance appraisal. He argued that top-level managers and low-level employees do not want to apply performance appraisal assessment for removing inside conflict and critics of the organization. In a research, 80 percent of employees were dissatisfied with performance appraisal assessment. Rewarding employees lead to affecting the colleagues of employees and achieving organizational goal. In addition, it also makes an employee more productive. Moreover, Performance appraisal plays a motivational role in case some do not misuse it (Marcellin, 2019). Mohamed Aly (2016) analysed the data of nurses. His finding showed that nurses are unhappy due to the top-level managers. Who delay the performance appraisal and this affects the productivity of the organization. Even though, he revealed that performance appraisal satisfaction has positive significant relations with internal motivation which significantly affect the organization's productivity. A study proved that usage of different performance appraisals has a motivational effect. The outcome of the organization even these tools help to identify the employees' merit and demerit (Idowu, 2017).

2.2 Work Motivation

Motivation could be divided into different parts. One of the well-known is intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation. The study of Deci (1971) as cited in (Gagné, 2014) proved that college students are significantly motivated by intrinsic motivation and positive feedback. However, extrinsic motivation is important in the place of work.

Some authors discovered that employees are motivated through different factors such as age, gender, education, race, etc... these had a significant impact on ranking (Islam & Zaki Hj. Ismail, 2008). Uzonna (2013) discovered that applying motivation to employees is different in every organization's culture because the organization gives value to different factors such as workplace, organization objectives, and general culture of the society.

Hitka et al. (2018) found out that gender and education of the employees have a significant difference. Moreover, the tangible remuneration exclusively salary and job security are also the most significant influential factors of the employees' work motivation. Ogunleye & Osekita (2016) discovered that the job status and sex of the employees do not have significant interaction with work motivation. However, Fjendbo (2020) found that females are significantly different at pecuniary rewards compared to males.

Some authors discovered that increasing age has a significant relationship with changing motivation form. For instance, older employees prefer to be motivated with easy tasks and flexibility with it, and self-autonomy of a task. However, some attributes remained unchangeable in the age changing, such as the same treatment of employees. Hence, it is concluded that changing age of employees has a direct relationship with changing motivation and satisfaction (Rožman et al., 2017). Some researchers discovered that the age of the employees played a moderator role in motivation and technology usage (Elias et al., 2012). However, Kuvass (2007) discovered that internal motivation is a mediator between the performance appraisal and work performance.

2.3 Research Problems

The Afghan government has too many problems in hiring and upgrading governmental employees. Some of these problems are biased and un-aware of applying the performance appraisal system and the employees cannot highly fairly perform their duties. This new central government pledged that they will eliminate those obstacles to have good governance and reduce these problems. Some studies proved that one of the reasons for less output of the organization is a low-performance appraisal that has a negative significant association with less output of the organization (Campbell et al., 1996).

Furthermore, performance connects organization policies and goals with employees (Williams, 2002). Therefore, the lower level objectives must be well defined which directly supports the goals and main objectives of the organizations (Williams, 2002) and these main objectives must support the administrative goal, organization strategy, training and development, and organizational feedback (Fletcher, 1997).

The internal and external motivation of MoHE employees is also affected by performance appraisal. Similarly, some researchers proved that these two elements also correlate with one another (Deci et al., 2001). This study aims to understand the performance appraisal satisfaction among the Ministry of Higher Education (MoHE) and to see its consequences on work motivation.

2.4 Research Objectives

- To examine the performance appraisal satisfaction as a predictor of work motivation among the MoHE employees.

- To compare all the four grades (3-6) of employees and gender of the participants on performance appraisal satisfaction and work motivation.
- To understand the age relationship with performance appraisal satisfaction and work motivation.

2.5 Hypotheses

Based on the above-mentioned objectives, the hypotheses are outlined below.

- H1: Work motivation would be significantly predicted by performance appraisal satisfaction.
- H2: There would be a significant interaction among grades and gender on performance appraisal satisfaction and work motivation.
- H3: There would be a significant association between the age of the participants and performance appraisal satisfaction and work motivation.

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Participants of the study

Afghan laws divide governmental employees into eight grades and each grade has five steps. A convenience sampling technique was used for data collection. The sample of participants comprised (60) employees of the Ministry of Higher Education of Afghanistan (MoHE). The data was collected in January 2019 from MoHE.

3.2 Exclusion Criteria

Afghan administrative system has political and non-political employees and political employees are hired with codified laws, therefore, political employees are excluded. Moreover, grades seven and eight are for Ajeer (cleaners, drivers and like this kind of work doers) on other hand grades one and two are less in quantity and they are in the presidency stage moreover, these employees are very less in amount, therefore, these two criteria employees were also excluded. Furthermore, Some MoHE's employees do not understand English therefore those employees were also excluded.

3.3 Inclusion Criteria

Both genders (41 male, 19 female) participated in a convenience sampling technique. Furthermore, most of the employees are from the 3rd, 4th, 5th and 6th grades (8, 25, 18, 9) respectively. And these employees participate in most of the work therefore these grades of employees are included. Age ranged from 22 to 37 years and its mean age was 27.35 of the participants.

3.4 Design of the study

The convenience sampling technique was used for data collection. Hence, most of the employees were very busy and did not have free time. The research time was also short for data collection.

3.5 Tools for data collection

3.5.1 Performance appraisal satisfaction scale

Crossman & Cook's (2004) standardized scale of performance appraisal satisfaction was used for data collection. It has 25 items that are self-reported by the respondents. These items measure respondents' performance appraisal satisfaction behaviour with a five-point Likert scale. The scale ranged from (1) strongly disagree to (5) strongly agree. Crossman & Cook (2004) reported the Cronbach alpha or reliability ($\alpha = 0.84$) which is very good.

Besides that, some items were slightly modified for the current research. This modification reflects the sentence and terminology to specify the organization. For instance, "I know how the performance appraisal satisfaction process helps [Company name] to achieve its strategic goals" modified to "I know how the performance appraisal satisfaction process helps MoHE to achieve its strategic goals". Next, the reliability and normalcy of the scale tested to assess the current research was ($\alpha = 0.827$), which means it is good for the prediction of the research and data was normally distributed.

3.5.2 Work Preference Inventory

Work motivation was measured through work preference inventory. Which was developed by Amabile et al. (1994). Which has self-reported 30 items. More exactly, this standardized scale measured two-dimension via Intrinsic Motivation (15 items) and Extrinsic Motivation (15 items) of the participants. Respondents were asked to measure their motivation perception on four points Likert scale. Which ranged from (1) rarely to (4) always. Cronbach's alpha was tested for this research the reliability of intrinsic motivation was ($\alpha = 0.676$) and extrinsic motivation was ($\alpha = 0.566$) was good and overall work motivation was ($\alpha = .759$) it is good.

3.6 Procedure

This research was conducted at the Ministry of higher education of Afghanistan (MoHE). Which is located in Kabul capital of Afghanistan. Administrative formalities and legality applied. In a well-instructed manner, the hardcopy of the scales was distributed for data collection. Written and verbally assured that this is academic research and its related rules and confidentiality of the participants applied. Hence, according to the planned action data was collected from the third, fourth, fifth, and sixth grades of employees and 60 participants responded.

3.7 Analysis of data

Regression analysis was used to understand the relationships among variables and the focus on the relationship between a dependent variable and some independent variables in other words predictors. Furthermore, numerical statistics data were analysed by SPSS version 24 through the two-way analysis of variance (two-way ANOVA) technique that compares means of more than two samples by using the F distribution.

RESULTS

Survey questionnaire results are as below.

Table 1

Liner regression of performance appraisal satisfaction as predictor of work motivation

R	R square	Adjusted R ²	Std. error	B	t	F	Level of sig	Min	Max
.331	.109	.094	8.63879	.287	2.669	7.125	.010	80.4	96.7

Dependent Variable: Work motivation (Intrinsic and extrinsic) Predictors: (Constant), Performance Appraisal Satisfaction

Table one depicts the linear regression analysis that was used to predict work motivation (intrinsic and extrinsic motivation) from performance appraisal satisfaction. Performance appraisal satisfaction explained a significant amount of variance in Work motivation, $F(1,58)=7.125$, $p=.01$, $R^2_{Adjusted}=.094$. The regression coefficient ($B=.287$, 99% CI [80.4, 96.7], $t=2.67$) indicated that an increase in one score of Performance appraisal satisfaction corresponded, on average, to an increase in work motivation score of .287 points.

H1: Work motivation would be significantly predicted by performance appraisal satisfaction.

The H1 is accepted because the Performance appraisal satisfaction did a significant contribution to the work motivation at the ministry of higher education of Afghanistan (MoHE) at 0.01 level of significance.

Table 2

Test of Between-subjects Effects of Performance appraisal satisfaction (Dependent variable)

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
grade	684.508	3	228.169	2.437	.075
gender	329.434	1	329.434	3.518	.066
grade * gender	677.678	3	225.893	2.413	.077
Error	4868.843	52	93.632		
Total	491716.000	60			

$R^2_{Squared} = .243$ ($Adjusted\ R^2_{Squared} = .142$)

Table 2 shows the main effect was observed among Performance Appraisal Satisfaction with Grade and Gender of the employees. There was not a significant effect among all variables such as Grade ($F(3,52)= 2.437$, $p>.05$), Gender ($F(1,52)= 3.518$, $p>.05$), meanwhile, the interaction of the enumerated variable and factors have shown also non-significant result as Grade and Gender ($F(3,52)= 2.413$, $p>.05$).

Table 3

Test of Between-subjects Effects of Work motivation (Dependent variable)

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
grade	104.383	3	34.794	.432	.731
gender	72.257	1	72.257	.896	.348
grade * gender	346.401	3	115.467	1.432	.244
Error	4192.340	52	80.622		
Total	461265.000	60			

$R^2_{Squared} = .137$ ($Adjusted\ R^2_{Squared} = .021$)

Table 3 depicts the main effect was observed among Work motivation (intrinsic and extrinsic) with the Grade and Gender of the employees. There was not a significant effect among all variables such as Grade ($F(3,52)= .432$, $p>.05$), Gender ($F(1,52)= .896$, $p>.05$), meanwhile the interaction of the enumerated variable and factors have shown also non-significant result as Grade and Gender ($F(3,52)= 1.432$, $p>.05$).

H2: There would be a significant interaction among grades and gender on performance appraisal satisfaction and work motivation.

The H2 is rejected because there is not a significant interaction among the Grades and Gender with performance appraisal satisfaction and work motivation.

Table 4

Descriptive statistics and Pearson Product-Moment Correlations of the Age and Performance Appraisal Satisfaction (PAS) and Work Motivation (WM)

	N	M	SD	Age	PAS	WM
Age	60	27.35	3.521	---		
PAS	60	89.93	10.44	0.22	---	
WM	60	87.21	9.076	0.09	0.33**	---

***P>.01 Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).*

Table 4 depicts Descriptive statistics and Pearson Product-Moment Correlations of the Age and Performance Appraisal Satisfaction (PAS) and Work Motivation. There is a positive correlation between the age and performance appraisal satisfaction (PAS) variables, $r = .22$, $N = 60$, however, the relationship of these variables is not significant ($p = .09$). Overall, participants' age does not appear to be associated with performance appraisal satisfaction.

Furthermore, there is a positive correlation between the age and work motivation variables, $r = .09$, $N = 60$, however, the relationship of these variables is not significant ($p = .457$). Overall participants' age does not appear to be associated with work motivation.

Moreover, there is a positive correlation between the performance appraisal satisfaction (PAS) and work motivation variables, $r = .33$, $N = 60$, however, the relationship of these variables is not significant ($p = .01$). Overall, participants' performance appraisal satisfaction does appear to be associated with work motivation.

H3: There would be a significant association between the age of the participants and performance appraisal satisfaction and work motivation.

The H3 hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there is no significant correlation between age and performance appraisal satisfaction (PAS) and work motivation variables.

DISCUSSION

The Performance appraisal satisfaction did a significant contribution to the work motivation at the ministry of higher education of Afghanistan (MoHE). In addition, Uzonna (2013) points out the motivation of employees is different from culture to the culture of an organization. Similarly, performance has a strong relationship proved with the high level of motivation (Kuvaas, 2006, p. 504). However, Marcellin (2019, p. 2) showed demerits of performance appraisal that destabilize the relation and communication among the employees of the organization, even though he proved that motivation of employees and performance appraisal directly support the organization productively. Similarly, another research also proved documents of performance appraisal positively support internal motivation which leads to organizational productivity also (Mohamed Aly, 2016).

Grades or ranking and gender of employees do not have significant interaction with performance appraisal and work motivation at MoHE. Similarly, Ogunleye & Osekita (2016) discovered that the sex of the employees does not have significant interaction with work motivation. However, Fjendbo (2020) found that females are significantly different at pecuniary rewards compared to males. Hitka et al. (2018) also found out that the gender of the employees has a significant difference. Some authors discovered that increasing age has a significant relationship with changing motivation form. For instance, older employees prefer to be motivated with easy tasks and flexibility. Hence, it is concluded that changing age of employees has a direct relationship with changing motivation and satisfaction (Rožman et al., 2017). An author revealed differently that the age of the employees played a moderator role in motivation (Elias et al., 2012). However, it is observed in the study that employees' age at MoHE does not have significant relations with performance appraisal satisfaction and work motivation.

LIMITATION

The data was just collected through the quantitative research method.

SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

It is highly recommended to research the larger sample to enhance the generalization of results. Furthermore, for diagnosing the exact reason the mix-method research is preferable to be applied.

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